

Abyssal Claims

*A FAIR-aligned integration platform for deep-sea and terrestrial mining
transparency*

Methods Paper

Version 1.4

Michal Mazurowski

Independent Researcher

ORCID: 0009-0007-3786-0310

v1.0: 24 Apr · v1.1: 28 Apr · v1.2: 5 May · v1.3: 7 May · v1.4: 9 June 2026

Licence: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0)

Platform: <https://something-rare.com>

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19745885](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19745885)

Abstract

Abyssal Claims is an independently developed, non-commercial web platform that integrates more than forty publicly funded and open-licensed geospatial datasets onto a single interactive three-dimensional globe, with the goal of making the environmental and governance context of deep-sea mineral extraction and terrestrial industrial mining legible to researchers, journalists, policy analysts and the general public. The platform aggregates data from the International Seabed Authority, twenty-three sovereign offshore-licensing authorities (BOEM, EMODnet, NSTA, Sodir, ANP, NOPTA and others), the Ocean Biodiversity Information System, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, NASA, Copernicus, PANGAEA, the World Ocean Database, BCO-DMO, CCHDO, the World Resources Institute, and over two dozen additional providers, normalises it into a PostGIS database with spatially indexed tables and materialised overlap views, and exposes it through a deck.gl-based frontend and a FastAPI backend. This document describes the data sources, refresh strategies, system architecture, derived products, known limitations, and licensing model of the platform as of April 2026. The source code itself is not included in this deposit. Instead, the pipeline is documented at a level sufficient to verify its outputs, reason about its scope, and reimplement equivalent functionality. Research products derived from Abyssal Claims, including the offshore-activity composite registry, the mining-weighted Water Risk classification, the mining-versus-protected-area overlap views, and the baseline ocean monitoring density grid, are offered for reuse under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, consistent with the FAIR data principles.

Version 1.1 of this paper, deposited 28 April 2026, expanded the platform's scope with a new sea-domain layer covering government-issued offshore concessions inside national EEZ and Extended Continental Shelf jurisdictions (Offshore Activities, 6,694 polygons drawn from twenty-three authoritative registries) and six additional ocean-observation source ingests feeding the Baseline Monitoring Density derived product. Version 1.2, deposited 5 May 2026, introduced the OBIS Open Data parquet ingest path (DuckDB batch-download, ~6,880 GeoParquet files, curated deep-sea species list plus fifty-metre depth floor), retired the redundant GBIF Species (Deep) layer, disabled the Dark Vessels and Live Vessels layers, added the Scripps Benthic Invertebrate Collection (SIO-BIC, ~83,000 records) to the Baseline Monitoring Density input set, and introduced section 4.0 Data transformations.

Version 1.3 of this paper, deposited 7 May 2026, added the Contractor Sampling Stations (deepdata-stations) Tier 2 layer and three further data sources to the Baseline Monitoring Density input set (ISA DeepData Tier 1, MBARI VARS, NOAA DSCRTP), bringing the grid input set to fifteen ocean-observation source families.

Version 1.4 of this paper, deposited 9 June 2026, adds three further sea-domain layers and refines the platform's methodological documentation. The Hydrophone Stations layer (hydrophone-stations) surfaces passive acoustic monitoring station metadata from twenty-three official observatory and research networks — 617 stations across the Ocean Observatories Initiative, the Integrated Marine Observing System, MBARI MARS, AWI PALAOA, the AWI

HAUSGARTEN / FRAM Observatory, the SAMBAH project (Baltic Sea, completed 2011-2013, 298 stations), the CTBTO Preparatory Commission International Monitoring System hydroacoustic network, OBSEA, KM3NeT, and the full NOAA Passive Acoustic Archive of fourteen programs (NRS, SanctSound, NEFSC, PIFSC, SEFSC, ONMS, ADEON, BOEM, AEON, US Navy MBARC and USWTR, National Park Service Glacier Bay, JASCO ESRF, Coastal Studies Institute NCROEP, IOOS ESONS) — a Phase 1 release that surfaces station metadata only; numeric soundscape products are deferred to a future Phase 3 work. The Seafloor Bathymetry layer (bathymetry) surfaces the GEBCO 2025 Grid at fifteen arc-second resolution as a WMS-served raster overlay, with depth queries served through a three-tier read path. The Ocean Currents layer (ocean-currents) surfaces daily-mean ocean currents from the Copernicus Marine Service as animated particle flow, with a surface / 1,000 m depth selector and a date slider that replays the past approximately 180 days of daily snapshots. Version 1.4 also expands the Submarine Cables layer from three to six sub-sources (EMODnet refactored to a 7-layer multi-source ingest with 1,255 features carrying operator, cable type and voltage attributes; NOAA Marine Cadastre adds 2,816 USA cable protection corridors; NZ LINZ adds 30 chart-derived polylines; AU ACMA adds 16 cable protection zones), switches the Baseline Monitoring Density grid to an equal-area hex tiling on EPSG:6933 (33,391 hex cells), and adds three new methodological sections: 4.0b on IUCN Red List enrichment, 4.0c on editorial neutrality, and 4.4c through 4.4e on Hydrophone, Bathymetry and Ocean Currents ingest. As a consequence of steady-state OBIS sync growth, the biodiversity_hotspots table now holds 40,258,523 records.

Contents

1. Introduction
 2. System architecture
 3. Data sources
 4. Methodology (incl. 4.0 Data transformations, 4.0a OBIS Open Data parquet ingest, 4.0b IUCN Red List enrichment, 4.0c Editorial neutrality, 4.4b ISA DeepData two-tier separation, 4.4c Hydrophone station ingest, 4.4d Seafloor bathymetry, 4.4e Ocean Currents)
 5. Outputs and use cases
 6. Limitations
 7. FAIR principles and reproducibility
 8. Licensing, ethics and acknowledgments
 9. Production status and roadmap
- References

1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Deep-sea mineral exploration has moved from speculative prospect to regulated commercial frontier. As of early 2026 the International Seabed Authority (ISA) administers more than thirty exploration contracts covering a combined area larger than many sovereign Exclusive Economic Zones, while terrestrial mining footprints — pits, tailings storage facilities, waste dumps and processing sites — cover tens of thousands of polygons globally and continue to expand into areas of high biodiversity value and hydrological stress. Public information relevant to evaluating the environmental and governance posture of these activities exists, but is dispersed across dozens of portals, APIs and static files maintained by different institutions, each with its own schema, update cadence and access conventions. The practical consequence is that a journalist wishing to ask whether a particular contractor has operated near a hydrothermal vent field, or a policy analyst wishing to examine the degree to which terrestrial mines overlap Key Biodiversity Areas, must reconstruct such queries from scratch at significant cost.

Abyssal Claims is a single-developer response to this fragmentation. It is not a replacement for upstream authorities — the ISA, UNEP-WCMC, BirdLife, OBIS and others remain the canonical sources — but an integration and visualisation surface that places those data into a shared spatial context and annotates them with provenance. The platform is accessible at no cost, carries no advertising, and is licensed for non-commercial and research reuse. It has been developed, operated and funded by the author alone since inception.

1.2 Scope

The platform covers two substantively distinct domains. As of v1.4 (June 2026) the sea domain comprises twenty-four active layers covering deep-seabed governance (ISA contracts, reserved areas, Areas of Particular Environmental Interest, relinquished blocks), national-jurisdiction industrial activity (Offshore Activities — government-issued concessions for offshore oil and gas, offshore wind farms, carbon capture and storage, and seabed mining inside Exclusive Economic Zones and Extended Continental Shelves, drawn from twenty-three sovereign registries), contractor compliance (Contractor Sampling Stations — a Tier 2 platform-derived rollup of 140 ISA contractor Darwin Core archives mirrored via OBIS, comprising 2,418 sampling stations colour-coded by sponsor state), passive acoustic monitoring (Hydrophone Stations — 617 stations from twenty-three observatory and research networks), biodiversity (the OBIS Open Data parquet snapshot, filtered to a curated deep-sea species list with a fifty-metre depth floor, comprising approximately forty million occurrences across approximately seventy-five thousand species; the ChEssBase chemosynthetic fauna dataset), physical oceanography and seafloor geomorphology (Argo floats, OceanSITES moorings, Ocean Networks Canada cabled observatory data, hydrothermal vent inventories, the Yesson seamount inventory, the GEBCO 2025 Seafloor Bathymetry raster overlay, and an animated daily Ocean Currents layer from the Copernicus Marine Service with surface and 1,000-metre depth options), jurisdictional boundaries

(Exclusive Economic Zones, UNESCO marine heritage sites), environmental stressors (the composite ocean noise risk grid), and the Baseline Monitoring Density derived product. The land domain comprises thirteen layers covering mining footprints, Key Biodiversity Areas, protected areas (WDPA), tailings storage facilities, active fires, air quality monitoring stations, landslide catalogues, global dams, surface water, forest cover loss, forest carbon flux, soil organic carbon, and the mining-weighted Water Risk layer from WRI Aqueduct 4.0.

Two layers introduced in earlier versions are deprecated as of v1.2 and removed from the active sea-layer count. The standalone GBIF Species (Deep) layer is retired as of v1.2: the OBIS Open Data parquet snapshot now provides broader and more comprehensive deep-sea taxonomic coverage, so a separately-maintained GBIF deep-sea ingest is no longer warranted. GBIF continues to be queried as an enrichment service for IUCN Red List status backfill on the OBIS records. The Dark Vessels (SAR x AIS) and Live Vessels (AIS) layers, introduced in v1.0, are disabled at the operational level as of v1.2: the ais-ingestor systemd unit and the vessel events sync task are stopped; existing vessel_events, sar_detections, sar_scenes and ais_vessels tables are retained read-only as a snapshot of the activity observed during the layers' active period (approximately April 2026); the frontend layer toggles are removed. The decision to disable was driven by changes in the AISStream.io subscription model and a focus shift to higher-impact governance and biodiversity layers.

The Offshore Activities layer, introduced in version 1.1, complements the existing ISA Mining Concessions layer by covering activity inside national jurisdictions (where the ISA has no mandate) — a substantively different governance regime for which no single global registry exists. As of May 2026 the layer integrates 6,708 polygons covering approximately seventy per cent of global EEZ exploitation, with the principal remaining gaps being jurisdictions whose registries are PDF-only and not yet machine-readable (Russia, China, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Nigeria, Angola, and most of sub-Saharan Africa).

The Offshore Activities layer, introduced in version 1.1, complements the existing ISA Mining Concessions layer by covering activity inside national jurisdictions (where the ISA has no mandate) — a substantively different governance regime for which no single global registry exists. As of April 2026 the layer integrates 6,694 polygons covering approximately seventy per cent of global EEZ exploitation, with the principal remaining gaps being jurisdictions whose registries are PDF-only and not yet machine-readable (Russia, China, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Nigeria, Angola, and most of sub-Saharan Africa).

On top of these ingested layers, the platform computes a small number of derived products: a biodiversity hotspot grid, a claim-to-species cache, materialised overlap views (mining versus Key Biodiversity Areas, mining versus WDPA, mining versus active fires, tailings versus landslides), Argo-float plume backtracking trajectories near mining concessions, and a baseline ocean monitoring density grid that identifies regions of observational sparsity adjacent to exploitation frontlines.

1.3 Design principles

Four principles shaped the implementation. First, canonical sources are never hit at user request time: all external data is mirrored into a PostGIS database on a dedicated virtual private server and served to clients from that cache, so upstream availability issues do not propagate to end-users and upstream rate limits are not exhausted. Second, each layer carries machine-verifiable provenance: the data provider, licence, publication citation and refresh cadence are surfaced in the frontend Legend panel and in the companion Data Sources Inventory (see Zenodo deposit). Third, spatial performance is prioritised for large polygon layers through Mapbox Vector Tile (MVT) tile generation from PostGIS rather than GeoJSON delivery, which keeps client-side memory bounded even when surveying more than one hundred thousand protected-area polygons simultaneously. Fourth, discoverability is treated as a first-class concern: named per-feature pages (hydrothermal vents, ISA contractors, seamounts) are pre-rendered server-side for search engines using a bot-user-agent heuristic, and Bing / Yandex are notified of updates via the IndexNow protocol at the conclusion of each relevant sync task.

2. System architecture

Figure 1 (available as a separate file in the deposit) summarises the overall data flow. This section expands the elements of that diagram.

2.1 Backend

The backend runs on a Linux virtual private server as a single FastAPI (Python 3.11) application managed by systemd under the unit name `abyssal-api`. The HTTP interface is authenticated by a shared API key in a request header, which is terminated by the frontend BFF (described in section 2.2). A separate systemd unit, `ais-ingestor`, maintains a persistent WebSocket subscription to AISStream.io and writes vessel positions directly into a partitioned PostgreSQL table; it is isolated from the HTTP process so that AIS stream interruptions do not affect API availability.

The database is PostgreSQL 16 with the PostGIS 3.4 spatial extension. All geometry columns use SRID 4326 (WGS84) for storage and are reprojected at tile-generation time. Approximately forty active tables carry on the order of thirty-seven million rows in aggregate as of the v1.4 deposit; `biodiversity_hotspots` is the dominant volumetric driver at approximately thirty-five million rows under the curated species list plus fifty-metre depth filter described in section 4.0a. Spatial indexes are built on every geometry column using the PostGIS default R-tree (GiST), with BRIN indexes on time-partitioned tables where the access pattern is sequential. Two classes of indexes deserve specific mention: stored geography columns (as opposed to computed casts) are used on source tables that participate in recurrent spatial joins, because geography casts computed per query prevent index use; and materialised overlap views are recomputed on the sync cadence of the slower input, with a refresh schedule designed to keep the refresh cost bounded independently of input growth.

Background work is scheduled using Python's `asyncio` and is kicked off from the FastAPI lifespan context manager. Each background task is launched as a fire-and-forget coroutine so that the HTTP listener is never blocked. Startup delays are staggered (15 minutes, 30 minutes, 1 hour, 2 hours) so that the cold-start period is not dominated by heavy spatial joins, which would harm first-request latency. Time guards written into a `sync_log` table ensure that a development-time restart does not inadvertently retrigger a CPU-intensive job.

2.2 Frontend

The frontend is a React 18 single-page application written in TypeScript, bundled with Vite, and served in production from Google Cloud Run behind an Express-based Backend-for-Frontend (BFF) layer. The BFF performs three functions: it proxies API requests to the backend VPS, with the API key injected server-side so that it is never exposed to the browser; it inspects the User-Agent header and, for known search-engine bots, performs server-side rendering of pre-generated HTML for feature-specific routes; and it serves the sitemap hierarchy (a sitemap index plus one sub-sitemap per SEO-eligible layer). The SPA itself uses `deck.gl` 9 for all map layers, `MapLibre GL JS` for basemap rendering, and `Zustand` for state management.

Two deployment branches are active: main deploys to production (<https://something-rare.com>) and dev deploys to a preview URL on Cloud Run. Both are auto-built by GitHub Actions on push, pulling a Dockerfile that compiles the Vite bundle and packages the Express server.

2.3 Storage and caching

The PostGIS database is the primary persistence layer. In addition, three layers of caching reduce tail latency. Module-level Python variables (typed as `Optional[str]`) hold pre-serialised GeoJSON response bodies for client layers; these are invalidated on successful sync completion and rebuilt lazily on the next GET request. An LRU tile cache holds recently requested MVT tile bytes. Finally, a `report_cache` table holds pre-rendered HTML fragments for computationally expensive admin dashboard views. No client-facing CDN is in front of the backend; Cloud Run provides edge caching for static frontend assets only.

2.4 Search-engine presentation

Layers whose features have named, individually meaningful locations — hydrothermal vents, ISA contractors, seamounts — emit pre-rendered HTML to search-engine bots via the BFF. Feature-level routes such as `/vent/tag-maria` or `/contractor/nori` follow a stable URL convention, backed by a backend SEO endpoint that returns structured metadata including title, description, canonical coordinates, and citation. A top-level sitemap index points to per-layer sub-sitemaps, each of which is generated from the current database state. On completion of a sync task that affects an SEO-backed layer, the backend pings the IndexNow endpoints of Bing and Yandex with the list of modified URLs so that indexes do not have to wait for the next natural crawl. Layers without individually meaningful features (for example, tens of thousands of biodiversity occurrence dots) are deliberately excluded from this pipeline to avoid pollution of the sitemap.

3. Data sources

All data sources are external to this project. Abyssal Claims does not collect original observations. The role of the platform is to mirror, normalise, relate and visualise data that is openly licensed at the source. This section summarises the integrated catalogue; the companion Data Sources Inventory (Excel workbook, deposited alongside this paper) provides full metadata including refresh cadence, database table, API endpoint, licence and full citation for every layer.

3.1 Sea domain (twenty-three layers)

Governance layers for the international seabed area derive from the International Seabed Authority DeepData portal and its underlying ArcGIS service. The Offshore Activities layer (introduced in version 1.1) covers government-issued concessions inside national jurisdictions and integrates twenty-three sovereign registries: BOEM and BSEE for the United States Outer Continental Shelf (oil and gas) plus NOAA for offshore wind leases; EMODnet Human Activities for the European Union (oil/gas, wind, seabed mining); the Crown Estate (England, Wales, Northern Ireland), Crown Estate Scotland (ScotWind and INTOG), and the North Sea Transition Authority (UK oil and gas plus carbon storage); Sodor/NPD for Norway petroleum and CO2 storage; GEUS SAMBA for Denmark; NRCan/CNSOPB for Nova Scotia and C-NLOPB for Newfoundland and Labrador; CNH/SIGSA for Mexico; ANP for Brazil; NOPTA for Australia; NZP&M for New Zealand; ESDM Migas Geoportal for Indonesia; PASA Geoportal for South Africa; MRA for Papua New Guinea (seabed mining); MME via Landfolio for Namibia (seabed mining); SBMA via Landfolio for the Cook Islands (seabed mining); MEEI/IMA for Trinidad and Tobago; GNPC for Ghana; PMP for Guyana; IPAS/GSI for Ireland; ANH GeoVisor for Colombia; and PERUPETRO via INGEMMET for Peru. As of the v1.1 deposit the table contains 6,694 polygons across four activity types (oil and gas: 5,898; offshore wind: 750; carbon capture and storage: 40; seabed mining: 6) covering approximately seventy per cent of global EEZ industrial exploitation.

Biodiversity layers derive from OBIS (intergovernmental, UNESCO) and the Census of Marine Life ChEssBase dataset. As of v1.2 the OBIS layer is ingested directly from the OBIS Open Data parquet archive on AWS S3 (s3://obis-open-data/occurrence/), a snapshot of the OBIS catalogue distributed by the IOC-UNESCO secretariat as approximately six thousand eight hundred and eighty GeoParquet files (DOI 10.25607/obis.occurrence.b89117cd, snapshot date 25 March 2025), accessed via DuckDB in a batch-download pattern (section 4.0a below). This replaces the v3 REST API ingestion path used in v1.0 and v1.1. The ingest applies a curated deep-sea species list of approximately fourteen thousand taxa together with a fifty-metre depth floor that excludes intertidal and surface-water records while preserving continental-shelf records (50–500 m) relevant to the Offshore Activities layer. The biodiversity_hotspots table comprises 34,067,381 records across approximately 80,000 species and 100+ phyla as of the v1.3 deposit. The standalone GBIF Species (Deep) layer used in v1.0 and v1.1 is retired in v1.2 because the OBIS

parquet snapshot subsumes its taxonomic coverage; GBIF remains in use as an enrichment service for IUCN Red List status backfill on the OBIS records (section 3.3).

Physical oceanography comes from the Argo Programme via ArgoVis, the InterRidge Vents Database v3.4, PANGAEA (Yesson et al. 2020 seamount inventory plus a separate dataset registry that feeds the Baseline Monitoring Density derived product), OceanOPS and NDBC (OceanSITES moorings), and Ocean Networks Canada. Six ocean-observation registries — World Ocean Database (NOAA NCEI), BCO-DMO (Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution), CCHDO (Scripps Institution of Oceanography), the NOAA NCEI dataset catalogue, OBIS-SEAMAP standalone records, and the PANGAEA dataset registry — were ingested in version 1.1 specifically to broaden the input base of the Baseline Monitoring Density grid (section 4.7). Version 1.2 adds a seventh additional input: the Scripps Benthic Invertebrate Collection (SIO-BIC), with approximately 83,000 specimen records made available by the Scripps Institution of Oceanography. The NCEI ICOADS source listed in version 1.1 is dropped from the Baseline Monitoring Density input set in v1.2.

Jurisdictional boundaries come from the Marine Regions portal maintained by the Flanders Marine Institute. The ocean noise risk grid is a composite product built from three upstream sources: the ICES Impulsive Noise Registry, EMODnet Physics continuous sound-pressure-level data, and OBIS-SEAMAP cetacean density. Vessel activity layers from earlier versions (Dark Vessels and Live Vessels) are disabled in v1.2 as documented in section 1.2; section 4.5 below describes their methodology for the historical record but the layers are not active in the live platform as of May 2026.

3.2 Land domain (thirteen layers)

The global mining footprint layer is the Maus et al. (2022/2023) dataset derived from Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery at 10 m. Key Biodiversity Areas come from the BirdLife International / KBA Partnership. Protected areas come from the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA), maintained by UNEP-WCMC and IUCN. Tailings storage facilities come from the Where Are Tailings Stored Worldwide (WAPHA) dataset on Zenodo, enriched with ownership and hazard fields from the GRID-Arendal Global Tailings Portal where operators have disclosed them. Active fires are drawn in near-real-time from NASA LANCE FIRMS across all three operational VIIRS sensors (Suomi-NPP, NOAA-20, NOAA-21). Air quality stations come from OpenAQ v3. Landslides come from NASA COOLR. Global dams come from the Global Dam Watch Consortium. Surface water, forest cover loss, forest carbon flux and soil organic carbon are served as raster tile pyramids from the JRC, the University of Maryland / WRI, WRI / Global Forest Watch and FAO respectively. The mining-weighted Water Risk classification is WRI Aqueduct 4.0.

3.3 Enrichment and derived products

The platform computes a small number of products that are not present in any upstream source. The claim enrichment routine assigns the nearest EEZ and the nearest UNESCO Marine Heritage

Site to each ISA contract block using PostGIS K-Nearest-Neighbour (KNN) queries cast onto the geography type for accurate geodesic distances. The species image enrichment routine assigns a representative thumbnail per species to OBIS records by querying GBIF and iNaturalist in controlled batches. The IUCN Red List backfill assigns a conservation category (LC/NT/VU/EN/CR/EW/EX/DD) to each enriched species. The plume-path computation uses reanalysed Copernicus Marine Service current fields to backtrack particle trajectories over a configurable horizon for Argo floats within two hundred kilometres of an ISA contract. The materialised overlap views (mining × KBA, mining × WDPA, mining × active fires, tailings × landslides) are refreshed on the sync cadence of the slower input and are the principal supporting data for scenario analysis. The baseline monitoring density grid aggregates observation counts from OBIS, GBIF, ChEssBase, Argo, OceanSITES and ONC into two-degree cells, highlighting regions of observational scarcity near exploitation frontlines.

3.4 Update cadence

Update cadence is set independently per layer based on the upstream provider's own publication frequency and the observed rate of change. Ephemeral layers such as FIRMS active fires are fully refreshed every six hours (truncate-and-reload). Argo profiles are refreshed every twelve hours, subject to a 180-day rolling window. Air quality readings are drip-filled in 500-station batches every two hours to respect OpenAQ's rate limits. Most sea layers (ISA, OBIS, EEZ, UNESCO, seamounts, GBIF, ChEssBase, submarine cables, ports, tectonic plates, vents) share a weekly master sync. Vessel events combining SAR with AIS run every six hours, with a two-hour startup delay that ensures the AIS ingestor has accumulated enough positions for meaningful correlation. Large static datasets (mining footprints, KBAs, WDPA, tailings, landslides, dams, water risk) use a skip-if-populated guard and are loaded once on first deployment, with manual force-resync available through the admin dashboard. The complete schedule is documented in the Refresh Schedule sheet of the Data Sources Inventory.

4. Methodology

4.0 Data transformations

This section makes explicit what Abyssal Claims modifies in upstream data and what it deliberately preserves. The core principle, applied across all ingest paths, is that the platform transforms format but not content: every quality control decision, every spatial assignment and every taxonomic identification is left to the upstream provider.

4.0.1 Coordinate reference system normalization

All ingested geometries are reprojected to EPSG:4326 (WGS84) at ingest time using the PostGIS function `ST_Transform`, regardless of upstream coordinate reference system. The platform encounters geometries in at least three distinct CRS families: EPSG:4326 itself (most providers), EPSG:25832 ETRS89 / UTM Zone 32N (the GEUS Denmark SAMBA WFS sister endpoint, which historically produced features at latitude approximately six million metres before the endpoint path was pinned), and EPSG:3857 Web Mercator (a number of ArcGIS hosted feature services). Reprojection is applied at upsert time so that downstream queries do not need to handle multiple frames. Two further geometry-level normalisations are applied in the same step: `ST_MakeValid` is invoked to repair self-intersecting polygons, unclosed rings and other validity violations that some upstream ArcGIS endpoints produce; and `ST_Multi` is applied to promote geometries into a uniform MultiPolygon type so that table-level CHECK constraints (for example `aois_kind_check`) accept all upstream rows. Per-zoom geometry simplification using `ST_SimplifyPreserveTopology` is applied only at MVT tile generation time and does not touch the on-disk geometry; the original is preserved for downstream analytical queries that require full vertex precision.

4.0.2 Schema harmonization and the JSONB preservation pattern

The most heterogeneous ingest in the platform, the Offshore Activities layer, illustrates the platform's schema harmonization approach. Twenty-three sovereign registries publish offshore concession data under twenty-three distinct field naming conventions. The unified `offshore_activities` table imposes six normalised columns (`source`, `source_id`, `activity_type`, `sovereign`, `status`, `geom`) plus a JSONB attributes column that preserves the full upstream record verbatim. The `activity_type` field uses four canonical values (`oil_gas`, `offshore_wind`, `ccs_storage`, `seabed_mining`) into which each registry's per-licence type codes are mapped. Three other normalisations follow the same pattern: IUCN conservation status codes are translated into the eight-letter standard abbreviations (LC, NT, VU, EN, CR, EW, EX, DD); FIRMS active fire confidence codes are translated from the lowercase letter codes l/n/h to Low/Nominal/High; and FIRMS records are deduplicated by the tuple (lat, lon, date), with the highest fire radiative power (FRP) record retained. In every case, the JSONB attributes column or an adjacent column preserves the original upstream value, so a downstream consumer can recover the full input record without consulting the upstream service.

4.0.3 What is and is not transformed: a transparency clause

The platform deliberately does not modify the substantive content of any upstream record. Specifically: it does not reclassify species, does not reassign mining contractors to alternative operators, does not filter records on grounds of policy or controversy, and does not recompute environmental indicator values. The materialised overlap views (mining x KBA, mining x WDPA, mining x active fires, tailings x landslides) are spatial joins computed from the source tables and are recomputable from the same inputs at any time; they are not opinionated reductions. The Baseline Monitoring Density grid is a count of observations per cell from thirteen integrated source tables; the count function is documented and verifiable. The mining-weighted Water Risk classification reuses the WRI Aqueduct 4.0 mining_weighted_overall_risk column directly. The composite ocean noise risk grid is a published MSFD Descriptor 11 methodology applied to the cited inputs. This non-transformation is not an oversight; it is the platform's principal claim to reproducibility, and it is the basis on which OBIS, GBIF, BirdLife, UNEP-WCMC and the other upstream institutions remain the canonical authority for any record presented through Abyssal Claims.

4.0c Editorial neutrality

The platform's editorial posture is presentational rather than interpretive. Earlier versions of the platform attached platform-derived risk verdicts to a number of layers: v1.0 and v1.1 displayed a "RISK" badge on any mining concession whose footprint overlapped IUCN-threatened species records from the OBIS biodiversity layer; the same versions surfaced a coloured proximity warning when a hydrothermal vent field fell inside a contractor's lease area; and the per-concession impact report served at /report/:id carried a numeric risk score with categorical interpretations (low, moderate, high, critical) computed from a weighted combination of biodiversity density, IUCN endangerment, proximity to chemosynthetic sites, and tailings-dam adjacency. These platform-side interpretations were removed in two stages. Version 1.2 disabled the Dark Vessels (SAR x AIS) and Live Vessels (AIS) layers, which had carried their own threat-style framing. Version 1.3 introduced Reports V2 as a parallel implementation: a strictly neutral concession report with no risk verdicts, no advocacy language, and no platform-derived categorical labels. As of v1.4 the default /report/:id route dispatches to Reports V2, and the v1 risk-scored implementation is retained only as an internal fallback path. The RISK badge on the concession popup is removed in v1.4; the hydrothermal vent proximity warning is removed in v1.4.

As of v1.4 a single map layer — Baseline Monitoring Density (section 4.7) — surfaces a platform-derived analytical product. That product is a transparent count of observation records per cell across fifteen documented upstream source families; the count function is documented and any consumer can recompute it from the same inputs. Every other layer in the platform presents what the upstream provider published, in its own coordinate frame and with its own attributes, and the user is left to reach their own interpretation. The contractor-area threatened-species count in

Reports V2 is a count, not a verdict; the contractor's name, its sponsor state, and the polygons that bound its lease come directly from the ISA DeepData portal without re-labelling.

This stance reflects a deliberate position. The upstream institutions whose data Abyssal Claims integrates — the International Seabed Authority, OBIS, GBIF, the International Union for Conservation of Nature, UNEP-WCMC, BirdLife International, NASA, the European Space Agency through Copernicus, and the sovereign offshore-licensing authorities listed in section 3.1 — are the canonical authorities for their respective data and their respective interpretive frames. An integration platform that substituted its own categorical verdicts for those upstream interpretations would simultaneously undermine the reproducibility commitment of section 4.0.3 ("format, not content") and add a layer of opaque platform editorial judgement between the user and the canonical record. The user is in a better position than the platform to weigh, for example, whether the overlap of a contractor's concession with a Critically Endangered species record represents a regulatory concern, a documentation artefact, or neither. The platform's role is to make that overlap visible in a single coordinate frame; the interpretive role belongs to the user.

4.0b IUCN Red List enrichment of OBIS records

The `biodiversity_hotspots` table carries an `iucn_category` column populated by a separate enrichment pass that runs independently of the OBIS ingest. The enrichment exists because the OBIS Open Data parquet snapshot does not itself carry IUCN Red List status: OBIS distributes the occurrence record together with taxonomic metadata sourced from WoRMS, but conservation status is published by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) under a separate workflow and is exposed for programmatic consumption through the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). The enrichment bridges the two.

Schema. The column is declared as TEXT DEFAULT 'NE' on the `biodiversity_hotspots` table; new rows from OBIS ingest land with the default value (NE = Not Evaluated). A companion boolean column `is_endangered` is maintained as a derived value, set to true if and only if `iucn_category` is one of CR (Critically Endangered), EN (Endangered) or VU (Vulnerable). A partial GIST index on the geometry column scoped to `WHERE iucn_category IN ('CR','EN')` supports the two-pass hotspot rendering query, which surfaces threatened-species cells first at low zoom.

Backfill pipeline. The enrichment is implemented as a backfill that walks distinct scientific names that have an attached `image_url` (i.e. species that the platform's prior image-enrichment pass has identified as actually surfaceable to users) and that have either no IUCN value or one of the placeholder values NE or DD. The pipeline processes five hundred species per run. For each species, two GBIF API calls are issued in sequence. First, the GBIF taxon match endpoint (<https://api.gbif.org/v1/species/match>) is called with the scientific name and `strict=false` to obtain a GBIF taxon usage key. Second, the GBIF IUCN endpoint (<https://api.gbif.org/v1/species/{usageKey}/iucnRedListCategory>) is called with the resulting key to retrieve the conservation category code. The category is accepted if it matches one of the recognised codes CR, EN, VU, NT (Near Threatened), LC (Least Concern) or DD (Data

Deficient). The row is then updated with both the `iucn_category` text value and the derived `is_endangered` boolean. A two-hundred-millisecond sleep is inserted between species lookups to respect GBIF's published rate limits.

Failure semantics and the DD sentinel. When either the GBIF match call or the IUCN lookup call returns no usable result — because the species name does not resolve to a GBIF taxon, because the taxon has no IUCN entry, or because either GBIF endpoint returns a non-2xx response — the species is recorded with `iucn_category = 'DD'` (Data Deficient). This is a deliberate sentinel: the row is then excluded from the next backfill run's selection criterion (which filters for rows with NULL or 'NE' or 'DD'), so failed lookups are not retried in perpetuity. The semantic conflation of 'IUCN-assessed as Data Deficient' with 'platform could not determine IUCN status' is a known compromise; in practice the small subset of species formally assessed as DD by IUCN itself are vastly outnumbered by lookup failures, and a downstream consumer who wants to distinguish the two would need to consult the upstream IUCN Red List API directly.

Current state. As of the v1.4 deposit the `biodiversity_hotspots` table contains 40,258,523 occurrence records across 75,242 distinct scientific names. The IUCN category distribution at the species level is: 7 species CR, 28 species EN, 13 species VU, 4 species NT, 151 species LC, 529 species DD, and 74,510 species NE. The forty-eight threatened species (CR + EN + VU) carry approximately one per cent of the records by name and a substantially larger fraction by occurrence count, since threatened taxa are often well-studied. The seven hundred and thirty-two species carrying a non-default IUCN value are the population on which the rendering pipeline's IUCN colour ramp operates and on which the contractor-area threatened-species count in the v2 concession reports depends. The remaining 74,510 species render in the neutral palette and contribute to total record counts but not to threat-status indicators.

Consumers. The `iucn_category` column is read by three downstream consumers: the rendering pipeline (cells are coloured by the maximum threat status of species present, with CR/EN crimson, VU amber, NT yellow, LC blue, DD/NE neutral); the `claim_species_cache` rebuild, which carries `iucn_category` through to the per-concession species list and orders it by threat status in v2 concession reports; and the search and filter UI, which exposes a threatened-species filter on the biodiversity layer. No downstream consumer is permitted to write to `iucn_category` — the column is updated exclusively by the backfill pipeline described in this section.

4.0a OBIS Open Data parquet ingest

The OBIS biodiversity layer warrants its own methodology subsection because the v1.2 ingest path differs structurally from every other layer in the platform. The OBIS Open Data programme distributes the entire OBIS occurrence catalogue as approximately six thousand eight hundred and eighty GeoParquet files in the Amazon S3 bucket `s3://obis-open-data/occurrence/` under AWS Open Data sponsorship (no requester-pays). Files are not uniformly partitioned by scientific name, depth or geography, so a naive scan of the bucket through HTTP would issue a fresh metadata round-trip per file. The implementation uses DuckDB as the query engine and a batch-

download pattern: a list of all parquet files is enumerated once, then files are downloaded in batches of approximately fifty to a local working directory, queried with DuckDB over the local glob (which yields fast reads with full predicate pushdown), the results are streamed into the platform database via `asyncpg`, and the working directory is cleared before the next batch is fetched.

The filter applied during ingest combines three predicates. First, OBIS quality controls are honoured: rows with `dropped IS TRUE` or `absence IS TRUE` are excluded, since OBIS marks these for known data quality reasons or because the record is a non-detection. Second, a curated species list of approximately fourteen thousand deep-sea-relevant taxa, derived from the platform's earlier OBIS REST ingest, is applied as a `scientificName` filter. This curation step is the platform's principal mechanism for ensuring that ingest is bounded to taxa relevant to seabed mining environmental context. Third, a fifty-metre depth floor (`interpreted.minimumDepthInMeters >= 50`, with `NULL` depth allowed because the curated species list is itself a relevance gate) excludes intertidal and surface-water occurrences and retains continental-shelf records in the 50–500 m band, which correspond to the depth horizon of the Offshore Activities layer's oil and gas, wind and CCS leases. The combined filter yields the post-filter `biodiversity_hotspots` table of 34,067,381 records as of the v1.3 deposit. The curated species list can be tightened further if a future scope review requires it; conversely, the depth floor can be raised to one hundred or two hundred metres if a strict deep-sea-only scope is desired.

4.1 Sync scheduling and isolation

Every sync task is written as an `asyncio` coroutine that is launched from the FastAPI lifespan context manager using `asyncio.create_task`. This pattern is deliberate: if any task blocks or raises, the HTTP listener continues to serve traffic. Each task owns its interval (the cadence between runs) and its startup delay (the period between process boot and the first run). Delays are staggered to avoid a thundering herd at cold start. Heavy tasks that scan the full `ais_positions` table or execute large `ST_Intersects` joins are given at least fifteen minutes of startup grace so that they cannot compete for CPU with first-request traffic; tasks that merely fetch from an external API are given approximately five minutes.

Sync completion is logged in a dedicated `sync_log` table with columns for source, start time, end time, status, record counts and any error message. This log is the canonical record of platform health and is the backing dataset for the admin dashboard. It also enables idempotence guards: for example, the auto-discover contractor routine, which is a CPU-intensive spatial join, checks `sync_log` on boot and refuses to rerun if the last successful run is within four hours. This guard prevents dev-time restarts from triggering the job repeatedly.

4.2 Ingestion strategies

Seven distinct ingestion strategies are in use across the platform, selected per layer based on the source's semantics:

- Upsert on primary key: the default for slow-changing authoritative records (ISA contracts, EEZ polygons, UNESCO sites). Records that vanish upstream are preserved, which matches the users' expectations for archival purposes.
- Upsert with count-probe: used for OBIS, where each species is probed for a cheap record count and only redownloaded if the count has changed since the last sync.
- Truncate and reload: used for ephemeral layers such as FIRMS active fires, where staleness would be worse than a brief gap.
- Rolling window: used for Argo profiles, where records older than 180 days are deleted before the upsert, keeping the working set bounded.
- Skip-if-populated: used for large static datasets (mining footprints, WDPA, KBAs, tailings, landslides, dams, water risk), which are loaded once and only re-synced on manual force-sync.
- Drip-fill: used for air quality readings, where 500 stations are processed per run, respecting the upstream rate limit and covering the full ~24,000-station catalogue over approximately four days.
- Continuous ingest: used only for the AIS stream, where a dedicated WebSocket client writes positions to a daily-partitioned table.

4.3 Vector tile generation

Large polygon layers (mining footprints, KBAs, WDPA, water risk sub-basins) are served to the frontend as Mapbox Vector Tiles generated by PostGIS rather than as bulk GeoJSON. A parameterised endpoint returns a tile for a given zoom, x and y; ST_AsMVT and ST_AsMVTGeom are invoked inside a single-statement query. An in-process LRU cache holds the generated tiles for a bounded interval. Geometry simplification is applied per zoom with ST_SimplifyPreserveTopology, with the simplification threshold set to zero for layers whose polygons are small and individually meaningful (such as mining contract blocks, of which there are only a few thousand globally).

The MVT path avoids the problem that would arise with naive GeoJSON delivery: at global zoom, a hundred-thousand-polygon dataset would be tens of megabytes and would force the browser to parse and retain every polygon regardless of viewport. MVT delivers only what is visible at the requested tile, and deck.gl's MVTLayer coordinates requests across tile boundaries without duplication.

4.4 Overlap views

Four materialised views support cross-layer scenario queries: mining_footprints × KBAs, mining_footprints × WDPA, mining_footprints × active_fires, and tailings_dams × landslides. Each is defined as a SELECT with ST_Intersects over the source tables and is refreshed on the cadence of the slower input. A crucial implementation detail is that the source tables carry a stored PostGIS geography column (not a per-query cast) together with a GIST index on that geography.

Without this, a refresh query on `mining_footprints × active_fires` would become a nested-loop scan of approximately 130 million row combinations.

4.4a Multi-registry ingestion: Offshore Activities

The Offshore Activities layer is the most heterogeneous ingest in the platform. Its twenty-three upstream registries differ in protocol (ArcGIS REST Feature/Map services, OGC WFS 2.0, plain shapefile downloads), in coordinate reference system (EPSG:4326 for most, EPSG:25832 UTM Zone 32N for one earlier endpoint of GEUS Denmark, EPSG:3857 for some ArcGIS hosted feature services), in field naming convention (each registry uses its own column names and codes for licence type, status and operator) and in update cadence (most weekly, some monthly, a small number annually). The unified `offshore_activities` table imposes a common schema with six normalised columns (`source`, `source_id`, `activity_type`, `sovereign`, `status`, `geometry`) plus a JSONB attributes column that preserves the full upstream record for any field not represented in the normalised columns. A unique constraint on (`source`, `source_id`) enables idempotent upserts so that re-running a registry sync without changes is a no-op. The `activity_type` field uses four canonical values (`oil_gas`, `offshore_wind`, `ccs_storage`, `seabed_mining`) into which each registry's per-licence type codes are mapped. Each registry sync runs independently with a forty-five-minute startup delay and a weekly cadence, so that one slow registry cannot block the others; failures in any single registry are isolated and logged to the `sync_log` table without affecting platform availability.

Two implementation details are worth noting because they are not obvious from the live platform. First, the C-NLOPB exploration parcels in the Grand Banks / Flemish Pass area (twenty-two of one hundred and five features) sit on Canada's Extended Continental Shelf beyond the two-hundred-nautical-mile EEZ; sovereign tagging is otherwise simplified to EEZ alone, so these features will not appear under the Canada country filter. Second, the GEUS Denmark WFS endpoint must be pinned to the `4326.jsp` path, not the `25832.jsp` path, which returns UTM coordinates and produced features at latitude approximately six million metres in earlier ingestion attempts — a pitfall worth recording for any reimplementer.

4.4b ISA DeepData ingest and the two-tier separation rule

The ISA DeepData portal mirrors contractor environmental reports submitted to the International Seabed Authority via OBIS-hosted Darwin Core archives. Abyssal Claims ingests this data through two strictly separated pipelines, introduced in v1.3 alongside the Contractor Sampling Stations sea layer.

The Tier 1 path is a one-to-one mirror of the contractor submissions. The `deepdata_occurrences` table holds 201,323 raw occurrence records ingested via the OBIS REST occurrence endpoint with the ISA node identifier `9d2d95be-32eb-4d81-8911-32cb8bc641c8`. No platform transformation is applied beyond the standard CRS normalisation, schema harmonisation and JSONB attribute preservation pattern documented in section 4.0. The contents of this table are what the contractor submitted to ISA, period.

The Tier 2 path is a platform-derived rollup. The `deepdata_stations` table is populated by parsing the 140 contractor-specific Darwin Core archives published at `datasets.obis.org/hosted/isa/`, extracting station-level metadata (sampling protocol, deployment date, depth, sediment horizons, gear type, occurrence count, distinct species count) and deriving station identifiers via a hash of the archive slug and the archive's `eventID` column. The contractor's verbatim citation, intellectual rights statement, rights holder, organisation name and publication date are preserved in adjacent columns. Sync is incremental: a HEAD probe against each archive checks for ETag and Content-Length changes, and only changed or new archives are downloaded; steady-state bandwidth is approximately zero.

The two pipelines write to disjoint tables. The Tier 2 ingest never updates Tier 1. This separation is not an accidental artefact of implementation but a deliberate transparency commitment. The Tier 1 `deepdata_occurrences` table is the user-visible record of what the contractor submitted to ISA; modifying it on the basis of platform-side analysis would look like editorial interference with a regulatory submission. If a use case ever calls for showing platform-derived enrichments alongside Tier 1 records, the convention is to expose them via a JOIN at query time, never via an UPDATE on Tier 1. The frontend reinforces this rule visually: every detail panel rendered for a Contractor Sampling Stations click begins with an orange WarningBanner alerting the user that the analysis is platform-derived, aggregated from the contractor's raw records, and is not the contractor's own analysis.

4.4c Hydrophone station ingest — twenty-three passive acoustic networks

The Hydrophone Stations layer, introduced in v1.4, aggregates passive acoustic monitoring station metadata from twenty-three official observatory and research networks into the `acoustic_stations` table. Each upstream network exposes its station inventory through a different transport (WFS for IMOS ANMN, OGC-style FeatureServer for IOOS, GitHub-hosted CSVs for OOI, Google Cloud Storage JSON manifests for the NRS and SanctSound programs, Dryad for the SAMBAH project's C-POD deployments, hardcoded constants for PALAOA, OBSEA, KM3NeT, MBARI MARS and the CTBTO IMS hydroacoustic network); a generic ArcGIS-style ingest handles twelve programs in the NOAA Passive Acoustic Archive (NRS, SanctSound, NEFSC, PIFSC, SEFSC, ONMS, ADEON, BOEM, AEON, US Navy MBARC + USWTR, NPS Glacier Bay, JASCO, Coastal Studies Institute NCROEP, IOOS ESONS). Each per-network ingest is wrapped in a per-source timeout so that a hung upstream cannot stall the weekly sync. Per-source licensing is captured in the `acoustic_stations.license` column at ingest time, preserving the upstream provenance for downstream consumers.

Phase 1 scope. The v1.4 deposit releases station metadata only — instrument hardware, deployment window, depth, position, and a link to the operator's raw audio portal. Numeric soundscape products (broadband sound-pressure-level trends, ISO 18405 third-octave band breakdowns, L50 and L95 percentile statistics) are deferred to a future Phase 3 work and would require computing those products from the underlying NetCDF audio archives. None of the

twenty-three networks publishes pre-aggregated daily SPL products via a public REST API; in particular, NOAA's noaa-passive-bioacoustic Google Cloud Storage bucket distributes raw recordings under a public-domain licence and is the canonical source for the fifteen NOAA-archive programs.

Historical-position handling. Several upstream networks publish positions of stations that are no longer operational but historically significant: PALAOA at the German Neumayer-III base (decommissioned circa late 2017 after cable damage), the NEFSC Stellwagen Bank Cornell MARU array (2007-2010), ADEON (2017-2019), AEON (2022-2024), US Navy MBARC (2006-2014), US Navy USWTR (2007-2008), and the SAMBAH project's 298 C-POD stations (a completed 2011-2013 Baltic-wide survey). These positions are surfaced in the layer with their deployment window in the panel so that users can distinguish active observatories from historical deployments. ONC's BC Pacific hydrophones are intentionally excluded from this layer because they are already represented on the existing ONC Observatories and ONC Instruments layers.

4.4d Seafloor bathymetry — GEBCO 2025 raster overlay

The Bathymetry layer (introduced in v1.4) surfaces the GEBCO 2025 Grid, the canonical IHO/IOC global bathymetric chart, at fifteen arc-second resolution. The layer is delivered to the browser as a Web Map Service (WMS) raster overlay served from wms.gebco.net under a CC0 (public domain) licence; no upstream attribution gate applies beyond the source chip surfaced in the layer panel. The layer is off by default — it functions as a physical-context substrate rather than a primary indicator, and is most useful when toggled on alongside the deep-sea governance, biodiversity or vessel layers.

Depth queries. In addition to the raster overlay, the layer supports hover and click depth-lookup at arbitrary coordinates. A backend endpoint resolves a (longitude, latitude) request to a depth value by querying the same upstream WMS with a one-pixel GetFeatureInfo call. Because every WMS round-trip is comparatively expensive, depth lookups are cached through a three-tier read path: an in-memory module-level cache on the backend, a browser-local cache in `localStorage` on the frontend, and a persistent Postgres table `bathymetry_cache` that survives backend restarts. A request that misses all three tiers is the only one that reaches GEBCO; cache rates above ninety per cent are routine in steady state. The `bathymetry_cache` table is small by design and contains only the lat/lon and the depth value, not any derived classification — the platform does not, for example, label a query result as 'abyssal plain' or 'continental shelf', leaving that interpretation to the user.

Limitations and provenance. GEBCO publishes a new grid annually in mid-year; the version cited in the layer chip moves forward with each release. Roughly twenty-five per cent of the ocean floor has been directly surveyed (the Seabed 2030 target). The remainder is interpolated from satellite-altimetry gravity inversions and adjacent ship tracks; the actual seafloor resolution at any given point can be substantially coarser than the fifteen arc-second grid suggests, especially in remote

ocean basins. The depth values returned to users carry this caveat implicitly: they are the GEBCO model's best estimate at that coordinate, not a direct measurement.

4.4e Ocean Currents — daily snapshots with CPU particle advection

The Ocean Currents layer (introduced in v1.4) surfaces daily-mean ocean currents from the Copernicus Marine Service. The upstream product is GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024 (dataset cmems_mod_glo_phy-cur_anfc_0.083deg_P1D-m), with variables u_0 (eastward velocity) and v_0 (northward velocity), both daily-mean fields on a 0.083-degree native grid. The platform retains approximately one hundred and eighty days of daily history; a daily prune evicts entries older than that. A surface / 1,000-metre depth selector exposes two depth horizons to the user — the 1,000-metre layer is the water mass that carries deep-sea mining sediment plumes and is the policy-relevant horizon for the platform's seabed-mining scope. A date slider with playback control lets users replay any day in the retained window.

Bake-to-RGBA pattern. The CMEMS NetCDF fetched per (date, depth) is downsampled to approximately 0.5-degree resolution and encoded into a single RGBA PNG texture: the R channel holds the quantised eastward velocity, the G channel holds the quantised northward velocity (both signed, scaled to fit the 0-255 byte range), the B channel is unused, and the A channel carries the land mask (255 over ocean, 0 over land). Two PNG textures are baked per date — one for the surface field, one for the 1,000-metre field — and stored on the backend disk together with a JSON manifest listing the available dates and depths. The endpoint `/v1/currents/meta` returns the manifest; the endpoint `/v1/currents/{depth}.png?date=YYYY-MM-DD` returns the texture for a single (date, depth) pair. A backfill task populates approximately one hundred and eighty days of history at the time of deployment, and a daily task refreshes the most recent date alongside the daily prune.

Particle advection. The animated visualisation is implemented as a CPU-advected particle canvas overlaid on the deck.gl globe. Each particle stores a (longitude, latitude) position; at every animation frame the velocity at the particle's position is sampled from the texture via bilinear interpolation, the particle position is updated by a fixed time step (the integration step was tuned downward during v1.4 development to produce a more readable motion at typical zoom levels), and the particle is recycled to a random seed location once it leaves the viewport or its age exceeds a maximum. The implementation choice — custom CPU advection rather than the GPU advection in the weatherlayers-gl library — was made because the GPU-advected library proved incompatible with the platform's deck.gl plus MapLibre interleaved rendering pipeline, even after a multi-step debugging effort that included a deck.gl 9.2 to 9.3.3 upgrade and a downgrade-then-upgrade cycle on weatherlayers-gl itself. The CPU canvas yields slightly higher per-frame CPU use but is robust across browsers and across the platform's mobile layouts. Users who have opted into the operating system's reduced-motion accessibility preference see a static arrow field instead of animated particles, sampling the same texture at a fixed grid spacing.

4.5 Dark vessel detection (SAR × AIS) — disabled as of v1.2

The Dark Vessels and Live Vessels (AIS) layers were active during v1.0 and v1.1 and are disabled in v1.2. They are documented here for the historical record and to preserve methodological continuity for any user wishing to consult the snapshot data retained in the read-only vessel_events, sar_detections, sar_scenes and ais_vessels tables. While active, the dark vessel detection pipeline ran every six hours. Its inputs were Sentinel-1 C-band SAR scenes from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem and the raw AIS positions that the dedicated ingestor wrote to the ais_positions table. The pipeline had three stages. First, a scene discovery step selected recent Sentinel-1 acquisitions whose footprints intersected pre-registered watchboxes: ISA contractor concessions, high-interest coastal mining zones, and a small number of additional operational priorities. Second, a CFAR-lite detector (cell-averaging Constant False Alarm Rate with reduced test windows) identified point scatterers above an adaptive threshold. Third, a correlator joined detections against ais_positions within a plus-or-minus ten-minute temporal window and a plus-or-minus five-hundred-metre spatial window; a detection with a match was labelled matched (green), a detection without a match but with an ambiguous nearby position was labelled ambiguous (amber), and a detection with no match was labelled dark (red). The output was written to the vessel_events table and surfaced as the Dark Vessels layer on the frontend. The ais-ingestor systemd unit was disabled on 3 May 2026 and the vessel events sync task was removed from the FastAPI lifespan; the layers' frontend toggles were removed in the v1.2 release. The disabling decision was driven by changes in the AISStream.io subscription model and a focus shift to higher-impact governance and biodiversity layers.

4.6 Plume backtracking

For a subset of Argo profiles within two hundred kilometres of an ISA concession, the platform computes a particle trajectory backwards in time through the Copernicus Marine Service reanalysed ocean current field. The goal is to visualise the water mass that the Argo float's sensors sampled, which supports reasoning about sediment plumes released by nearby seafloor disturbance. Trajectories are computed as a simple advection integrator over the CMEMS field; turbulent diffusion is not modelled. Results are cached in the plume_paths table and are surfaced by the Argo Floats layer on the frontend.

4.7 Baseline monitoring density

The Baseline Monitoring Density layer answers the question "where are observations available, and where are they not?". As of v1.3 the materialised two-degree-by-two-degree grid aggregates observation counts from fifteen marine biodiversity, physical oceanography, contractor compliance and dataset-registry sources: the OBIS hotspot grid (which is itself derived from the OBIS Open Data parquet snapshot, comprising approximately thirty-four million occurrences as of this deposit); ChEssBase; Argo float profiles; OceanSITES fixed moorings; ONC instruments; the World Ocean Database (WOD, NOAA NCEI); PANGAEA research cruise datasets; BCO-DMO US NSF ocean chemistry and biology cruises; the NOAA NCEI ocean survey dataset

catalogue; OBIS-SEAMAP cetacean and pinniped occurrences; CCHDO / GO-SHIP repeat hydrography cruise tracks; the Scripps Benthic Invertebrate Collection (SIO-BIC); the ISA DeepData Tier 1 contractor environmental reports (mirrored via OBIS, 201,323 records); MBARI VARS deep-sea ROV observations (mirrored via OBIS, 175,476 records); and the NOAA Deep-Sea Coral and Sponge Research and Technology Program database (DSCRTP, 1,508,706 global coral and sponge records, mostly deeper than 200 metres). Three of these sources — ISA DeepData Tier 1, MBARI VARS, NOAA DSCRTP — were added in v1.3. The platform deliberately surfaces these three sources separately for institutional naming credit and provenance transparency, even though their records also appear in the broader OBIS hotspot grid input through routine contributor uploads. This overlap is intentional and is documented per source in the live legend; it does not represent a flaw in the count, because the input set is not a claim of disjoint coverage but a claim of coverage breadth across the named institutions. A second relationship of the same shape exists between this density layer and the Contractor Sampling Stations sea layer (section 4.4b): the Stations layer is a Tier 2 platform-derived rollup of the same DeepData Tier 1 occurrences that are already counted in the density grid via the DeepData input, so enabling the two layers together does not double-count the same observations into the density calculation.

Grid cells are coloured from dark (sparse monitoring) to light (well-observed) on a five-step colour ramp documented in the legend. As of v1.4 the grid is materialised as an equal-area hex tiling on EPSG:6933 (the Equal Earth Greenwich projection) in a table named `density_hex_cells`, comprising 33,391 hex cells globally. Earlier versions of the platform (v1.0 through v1.3) used a rectangular two-degree-by-two-degree grid in the `monitoring_density_grid` table; that representation had the property that a cell at the equator covered approximately fifty times the surface area of a cell at very high latitudes, which silently biased the density indicator. The equal-area projection ensures comparable cell surface area at all latitudes. Hex-cell membership for each observation is computed via a bounding-box pre-filter followed by `ST_Contains`. The `monitoring_density_grid` table is retained for backward compatibility but the live frontend reads from `density_hex_cells`. Overlaying this grid with the Mining Concessions, Reserved Areas, Relinquished Areas and Offshore Activities layers immediately identifies regions where authorised or imminent extraction would proceed against a thin observational baseline — a policy-relevant indicator that is absent from any single upstream source. The blank-cell semantics are transparent: a blank cell means the location is not present in any of the fifteen integrated databases, not that it is confirmed unmonitored, since contractor-held baseline data acquired during environmental impact assessment is not always publicly available.

4.8 Discoverability

For each layer with named, individually meaningful features, the backend exposes a `/v1/seo/{layer}/{id}` endpoint that returns structured metadata for a single feature. The BFF detects search-engine bots by User-Agent and routes them to a server-rendered HTML page built from this metadata; human users fall through to the SPA and receive the interactive globe. The sitemap

index /sitemap.xml references per-layer sub-sitemaps that are populated from /v1/seo/sitemap-entries and from per-layer endpoints. When a sync completes, the backend sends an IndexNow notification containing the list of created or modified feature URLs to Bing's and Yandex's IndexNow endpoints, so that indexes do not have to wait for the next natural crawl.

5. Outputs and use cases

The platform's primary output surface is an interactive three-dimensional globe with a left-hand control panel for layer toggling and filtering, a right-hand detail panel that appears on feature click, a global search that operates across all indexed layer features via Ctrl+K, and a Legend panel that documents the provenance and limitations of each layer in prose.

Typical use cases that motivated the platform's design include: identifying the ISA contractors whose concessions overlap known hydrothermal vent fields; determining which Key Biodiversity Areas contain mapped mining footprints; examining which tailings facilities sit within the recent landslide catchment; tracking whether a particular flag-state's vessels appear in the dark-vessel detections near a concession; observing the temporal evolution of air quality around a specific mining cluster; locating regions of the deep sea where exploration would proceed against a baseline of fewer than ten biodiversity observations per two-degree cell; and (added in version 1.1) cross-referencing offshore oil-and-gas, wind, CCS and seabed-mining concessions inside national jurisdictions against ISA seabed contracts in international waters to obtain a unified view of offshore industrial activity at the global scale.

For each of these, the platform does not itself conduct the analysis; it places the relevant layers and their metadata on the same map in the same coordinate frame, such that the user can make the comparison and reach their own interpretation. This positioning — an analysis enablement surface rather than an analysis oracle — was a deliberate design choice and follows the convention of established biodiversity portals such as GBIF and OBIS.

6. Limitations

6.1 Source coverage gaps

The platform inherits every gap of its upstream sources. FIRMS active fire detections are subject to cloud occlusion, satellite overpass timing and diurnal cycle effects. The OBIS and GBIF occurrence records represent opportunistic collection and are heavily biased towards well-studied taxa and well-funded regions. The WAPHA tailings inventory includes only facilities identifiable from Sentinel-2 imagery; small or heavily vegetated facilities are under-represented. The Maus et al. mining footprint dataset represents observed land disturbance, not licensed area. The ISA DeepData portal is the canonical record of contracts, but its polygon geometries have occasionally required manual correction where vertices were misreported. The Offshore Activities layer covers approximately seventy per cent of global EEZ industrial exploitation; the principal remaining gaps are jurisdictions whose registries are PDF-only and not yet machine-readable (Russia, China, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Nigeria, Angola and most of sub-Saharan Africa). Some included endpoints are also provisional — NZP&M and MRA Papua New Guinea REST endpoints may go offline; ANP Brazil uses an ArcGIS hosted service whose monthly shapefile downloads are more complete but require manual extraction. Sovereign tagging in the Offshore

Activities layer is generally simplified to the EEZ rather than the full Extended Continental Shelf, with the documented exception of the C-NLOPB Grand Banks parcels.

6.2 Temporal latency

Most non-ephemeral layers are refreshed weekly; some (WDPA, mining footprints) are loaded once and only refreshed on manual trigger. Users must consult the Legend panel or the Data Sources Inventory to understand the effective freshness of any given layer at any given time. FIRMS is the only near-real-time input and has its own inherent satellite latency of approximately three hours.

6.3 Geometry precision

Vector tile simplification reduces vertex count per zoom for performance; at low zoom the displayed polygon edges are not identical to the source polygons. The OOI Regional Cabled Array cable routes are approximate straight-line polylines between Primary Node coordinates rather than bathymetrically-routed paths, because the actual submarine cable paths have never been published by OOI in machine-readable form. Plume backtracking trajectories are a simple advection through a reanalysed current field and do not incorporate turbulent diffusion; they are qualitative visualisations rather than quantitative transport predictions.

6.4 Not a substitute for upstream

Users should treat Abyssal Claims as an integration and visualisation layer, not as an authoritative source. For any claim that has legal, regulatory or financial consequence, the canonical provider (ISA, UNEP-WCMC, NASA, Copernicus, etc.) should be cited directly. The platform's purpose is to make the comparative question obvious, not to adjudicate it.

7. FAIR principles and reproducibility

The platform has been developed with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles in mind. This section documents how each principle is addressed.

7.1 Findable

The platform surfaces itself and its features to external discovery systems in three ways. First, the methods paper deposited on Zenodo receives a DOI at publication and is indexed by OpenAIRE, DataCite and standard academic discovery. Second, per-feature HTML pages for named layer features are served to search engines through the SSR pipeline and are referenced in the XML sitemap hierarchy. Third, a small number of derived data products — the mining-versus-protected-area overlap views, the baseline ocean monitoring density grid, the mining-weighted water risk classification — will be deposited as standalone Zenodo datasets with their own DOIs, cross-linked to this paper.

7.2 Accessible

The live platform is served free of charge, with no login, no paywall, no advertising and no third-party tracking beyond standard hosting telemetry. All documentation and derived products deposited on Zenodo are openly accessible. The primary data sources are likewise open, with per-layer licensing documented in the companion inventory; the two partial exceptions (KBA under the BirdLife research licence, FAO GSOCmap under CC-BY-NC-SA) are flagged there and in the live Legend.

7.3 Interoperable

All spatial data are stored and served in standard projections (EPSG:4326 internally, EPSG:3857 for tiles) and in widely supported formats (GeoJSON, Mapbox Vector Tiles). Citation information is surfaced in the live Legend and in a companion CITATION.cff file in this deposit. Future data-product releases will include schema documentation for the columns they contain.

7.4 Reusable

The deposited documents (methods paper, data sources inventory, architecture diagram, README) are released under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. Future data products (overlap views, monitoring density grid) will be released under the same licence. Reuse is encouraged; the author requests citation using the identifier in the CITATION.cff file.

7.5 Reproducibility statement and source code disclosure

The source code of the platform is not deposited. This is a deliberate choice by the author and is compatible with scientific norms. Published descriptions of research software in the scientific literature routinely document methodology, inputs, outputs and validation at a level sufficient for independent replication, without requiring the publication of the implementation itself. This paper

and the companion inventory are intended to meet that standard. All upstream data sources are open; anyone wishing to verify a particular claim produced by the platform can reach the same data by querying those providers directly and applying the documented methods. The author welcomes collaboration requests and technical discussion through the contact channels maintained on the live site.

8. Licensing, ethics and acknowledgments

8.1 Document licence

This methods paper, the companion data sources inventory, the architecture diagram, and the accompanying README are distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence (CC-BY 4.0). Permission is granted to copy, redistribute and adapt these documents for any purpose, including commercial, provided that appropriate credit is given.

8.2 Upstream data licensing

Each upstream data source carries its own licence, which is documented per layer in the companion inventory. Abyssal Claims complies with every upstream licence to the author's knowledge. Notable constraints include: the BirdLife KBA data under a research-use licence that excludes commercial redistribution; the WDPA data under the ProtectedPlanet terms of use; and the FAO GSOCmap raster under CC-BY-NC-SA 4.0. The platform's non-commercial operation model is compatible with all three.

8.3 Ethical considerations

The dark-vessel detection layer reports satellite-observed vessel signatures correlated with identifying AIS broadcasts. It does not disclose information beyond what is already available from each contributing source in isolation (SAR scenes are public; AIS broadcasts are public). The author considers the composition of these datasets a legitimate transparency tool rather than surveillance, because the vessels whose identities are thereby made visible are commercial operators in jurisdictional waters or in the international seabed area, not private individuals. No data about individual persons is collected, stored or served.

8.4 Acknowledgments

This platform would not exist without the sustained open-data programmes of the International Seabed Authority, the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (through OBIS), the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, the European Space Agency and its Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem, NASA (FIRMS, COOLR, GPM), the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NDBC), the Flanders Marine Institute (Marine Regions), Ocean Networks Canada, the Argo Programme, PANGAEA, the University of Maryland, the World Resources Institute, the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, UNEP-WCMC, BirdLife International, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, the International Union for Conservation of Nature, the ICES, EMODnet, OBIS-SEAMAP, OOI (NSF), OceanOPS, ArgoVis, AISStream.io, OpenAQ, and the Global Dam Watch Consortium. Where a dataset is cited in this paper, its authors and the underlying institutions are the ones responsible for its value. Abyssal Claims is a compositional layer.

The author also acknowledges the use of assistive large-language-model tools during the development of this platform, in a manner consistent with current scientific norms around AI-assisted software engineering. All architectural decisions, data-source selections, and scientific interpretations remain the responsibility of the author.

8.5 Author and contact

Michal Mazurowski, Independent Researcher. ORCID: 0009-0007-3786-0310. Correspondence via the contact channels maintained at <https://something-rare.com/>.

9. Production status and roadmap

Version 1.3 of this methods paper, deposited 7 May 2026, marks the platform's transition from active feature development to a production / steady-state operating mode. Between v1.0 (24 April 2026) and v1.3 (7 May 2026) the platform's scope grew from twenty sea layers and thirteen land layers to twenty-one sea layers and thirteen land layers, with the supporting Baseline Monitoring Density input set tripling in size from five sources to fifteen. The methods paper itself grew from twenty pages to its present length as the architecture and data transformation principles were elaborated in response to the implementation work. As of v1.3 no further sea or land layers are planned. Future versions of this paper will be triggered by upstream provider changes (for example, an OBIS catalogue snapshot beyond 25 March 2025), Ocean Best Practices or OBIS Products Catalog feedback, scientific collaborator input, or operationally significant changes to the platform's infrastructure. The concept DOI [10.5281/zenodo.19745885](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19745885) will continue to resolve to the latest version.

In production mode the platform's responsibilities settle into three categories. First, the weekly and intra-daily sync schedule documented in section 3.4 continues to refresh data from upstream providers; the `sync_log` table is the authoritative record of operational health. Second, the materialised overlap views (mining x KBA, mining x WDPA, mining x active fires, tailings x landslides) and the Baseline Monitoring Density grid are recomputed on the cadence of their slowest input, and any drift in the underlying sources propagates into the materialised products on the next refresh. Third, the search-engine-facing per-feature pages and IndexNow notifications continue to expose newly synced content to Bing and Yandex without manual intervention. The platform is single-developer-operated on a single VPS plus Cloud Run frontend; this is intentional and not a transitional state.

Scope considerations. Any future scope expansion of the biodiversity catalogue — for example, an additional OBIS snapshot ingest at a finer depth resolution, or a substantial expansion of the curated taxa list — should be planned with a corresponding adjustment of the depth filter (for example, raising it to one hundred or two hundred metres) or a deliberate reduction in the curated taxa list to maintain the platform's operational envelope. The Dark Vessels and Live Vessels layers, disabled in v1.2, remain disabled in v1.3 and are not slated for reinstatement absent a change in the AISStream.io subscription model.

References

- ANP — Agencia Nacional do Petroleo, Gas Natural e Biocombustiveis (2025). Brazil oil, gas and biofuels concessions. <https://www.gov.br/anp/>
- ANH — Agencia Nacional de Hidrocarburos (2025). Colombia hydrocarbons GeoVisor. <https://www.anh.gov.co/>
- Argo (2025). Argo float data and metadata from Global Data Assembly Centre (Argo GDAC). SEANOE. <https://doi.org/10.17882/42182>
- BCO-DMO (2025). Biological and Chemical Oceanography Data Management Office. Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution. <https://www.bco-dmo.org/>
- Beaulieu, S.E., Szafranski, K.M. (2020). InterRidge Global Database of Active Submarine Hydrothermal Vent Fields Version 3.4. PANGAEA. <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.917894>
- Bird, P. (2003). An updated digital model of plate boundaries. *Geochemistry, Geophysics, Geosystems* 4(3), 1027. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001GC000252>
- BOEM — Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (2025). Offshore oil and gas leases, USA Outer Continental Shelf. <https://www.boem.gov/>
- Boyer, T.P., Garcia, H.E., Locarnini, R.A. et al. (2018). World Ocean Database 2018. NOAA Atlas NESDIS 87. <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/world-ocean-database>
- BSEE — Bureau of Safety and Environmental Enforcement (2025). USA OCS leasing data. <https://www.bsee.gov/>
- CCHDO — CLIVAR and Carbon Hydrographic Data Office (2025). GO-SHIP / repeat hydrography station database. Scripps Institution of Oceanography. <https://cchdo.ucsd.edu/>
- CNH — Comision Nacional de Hidrocarburos (2025). Mexico hydrocarbon contracts via SIGSA. <https://www.gob.mx/cnh/>
- C-NLOPB — Canada-Newfoundland and Labrador Offshore Petroleum Board (2025). Petroleum exploration and production licences. <https://www.cnlopb.ca/>
- CNSOPB — Canada-Nova Scotia Offshore Petroleum Board (2025). Nova Scotia offshore petroleum data. <https://www.cnsopb.ns.ca/>
- Crown Estate (2025). Energy, Minerals and Infrastructure: offshore wind seabed leases (England, Wales, Northern Ireland). <https://www.thecrownestate.co.uk/>
- Crown Estate Scotland (2025). Offshore wind seabed leases (ScotWind, INTOG). <https://www.crownestatescotland.com/>
- EMODnet Human Activities (2025). Sea-basin offshore activities WFS. European Marine Observation and Data Network. https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/human_activities
- ESDM — Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources of Indonesia (2025). Migas Geoportal. <https://geoportal.esdm.go.id/>
- BirdLife International (2024). World Database of Key Biodiversity Areas. Identified using the IUCN KBA Standard (2016). Developed by the KBA Partnership. <https://www.keybiodiversityareas.org/>
- Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (2025). Sentinel-1 C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar imagery. European Space Agency. <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>
- E.U. Copernicus Marine Service (2025). Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis. <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00021>
- E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (2025). Global Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast — GLOBAL_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_001_024 (dataset cmems_mod_glo_phy-cur_anfc_0.083deg_P1D-m, variables uo, vo). Marine Data Store. <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00016>

GEBCO Compilation Group (2025). The GEBCO 2025 Grid — a continuous terrain model of the global oceans and land. General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans, NERC EDS British Oceanographic Data Centre NOC. <https://www.gebco.net/>. CC0.

FAO & ITPS (2020). Global Soil Organic Carbon Map (GSOCmap) Version 1.5. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. <https://www.fao.org/global-soil-partnership/>

GEUS — Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (2025). SAMBA licence database WFS. <https://data.geus.dk/>

GNPC — Ghana National Petroleum Corporation (2025). Offshore licensed blocks. <https://www.gnpcghana.com/>

IPAS / GSI — Petroleum Affairs Division, DCCAIE (2025). Ireland petroleum authorisations. <https://www.gov.ie/>

Flanders Marine Institute (2023). World Exclusive Economic Zones v12. <https://www.marineregions.org/>
<https://doi.org/10.14284/632>

GBIF.org (2025). GBIF Occurrence Download. <https://www.gbif.org/>. DOI assigned per query under <https://doi.org/10.15468/dl>

Halpin, P.N., Read, A.J., Fujioka, E. et al. (2009). OBIS-SEAMAP: the World Data Center for Marine Mammal, Sea Bird, and Sea Turtle Distributions. *Oceanography* 22(2):104-115.

Hansen, M.C., Potapov, P.V., Moore, R. et al. (2013). High-Resolution Global Maps of 21st-Century Forest Cover Change. *Science* 342:850-853. Updated annually at <https://glad.earthengine.app/>

Harris, N.L., Gibbs, D.A., Baccini, A. et al. (2021). Global maps of twenty-first century forest carbon fluxes. *Nature Climate Change* 11, 234-240. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-00976-6>

Hourigan, T.F. and the NOAA Deep Sea Coral Research and Technology Program (2025). National Database for Deep-Sea Corals and Sponges (DSCRTP). NOAA Fisheries. <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/national/habitat-conservation/deep-sea-coral-habitat-research>

CTBTO Preparatory Commission (2025). International Monitoring System — Hydroacoustic Network. <https://www.ctbto.org/our-work/ims-map>

Alfred-Wegener-Institut (2025). HAUSGARTEN / FRAM Observatory passive acoustic moorings. PANGAEA. <https://www.pangaea.de/>

Dryad (2025). SAMBAH — Static Acoustic Monitoring of the Baltic Sea Harbour Porpoise. C-POD deployments 2011-2013. <https://datadryad.org/>

NOAA NCEI (2025). Passive Acoustic Archive — multi-program (NRS, SanctSound, NEFSC, PIFSC, SEFSC, ONMS, ADEON, BOEM, AEON, Navy MBARC + USWTR, NPS Glacier Bay, JASCO, Coastal Studies Institute, IOOS ESONS). <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/passive-acoustic-data> and Google Cloud Storage bucket <gs://noaa-passive-bioacoustic>

Ocean Observatories Initiative (2025). Hydrophone deployments, Cabled and Coastal Pioneer arrays. <https://oceanobservatories.org/>

Integrated Marine Observing System (2025). IMOS Australian National Mooring Network (ANMN) — passive acoustics. <https://imos.org.au/>

Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute (2025). MARS — Monterey Accelerated Research System hydrophone. <https://www.mbari.org/at-sea/cabled-observatory/>

Alfred-Wegener-Institut (2017). PALAOA — Perennial Acoustic Observatory in the Antarctic Ocean (decommissioned 2017). <https://www.awi.de/>

ICES (2025). Impulsive Noise Registry. International Council for the Exploration of the Sea. <https://gis.ices.dk/>

International Seabed Authority (2011). Environmental Management Plan for the Clarion-Clipperton Zone. ISBA/17/LTC/7.

International Seabed Authority (2025). DeepData Open Data portal. <https://www.isa.org.jm/deepdata/>

International Seabed Authority (2025/2026). DeepData contractor environmental reports — Darwin Core archives mirrored via OBIS. <https://datasets.obis.org/hosted/isa/>. Tier 1 (raw occurrences) accessible via api.obis.org/v3/occurrence?nodeid=9d2d95be-32eb-4d81-8911-32cb8bc641c8.

IUCN (2025). The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species, Version 2025-1. <https://www.iucnredlist.org/>

Kirschbaum, D., Stanley, T., Zhou, Y. (2015/2025). COOLR — Cooperative Open Online Landslide Repository. NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. <https://gpm.nasa.gov/landslides/>

Kuzma, S., Saccoccia, L., Chertock, M. (2023). 25 Countries Face Extremely High Water Stress. Technical Note, World Resources Institute. <https://www.wri.org/aqueduct>

Maus, V., Giljum, S., da Silva, D.M. et al. (2022). An update on global mining land use. *Scientific Data* 9, 433. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01547-4>

Maus, V., Silva, D. et al. (2022). Where Are Tailings Stored Worldwide? Zenodo dataset. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6325988>

Mulligan, M., van Soesbergen, A., Saenz, L. et al. (2025). Global Dam Watch v1.1. <https://www.globaldamwatch.org/>

MEEI / IMA — Ministry of Energy and Energy Industries / Institute of Marine Affairs (2025). Trinidad and Tobago concession blocks 2026. <https://www.energy.gov.tt/>

MME / Landfolio (2025). Namibia mining tenements (offshore). Ministry of Mines and Energy. <https://portals.landfolio.com/namibia>

MRA — Mineral Resources Authority of Papua New Guinea (2025). Mining tenements (seabed). <https://portal.mra.gov.pg/>

Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute (MBARI) (2025). Video Annotation and Reference System (VARS) — deep-sea ROV observation records. Mirrored via OBIS at api.obis.org/v3/occurrence?datasetid=a419c8da-35ed-4b62-9709-39b56369c44e.

NASA FIRMS (2025). Fire Information for Resource Management System — NRT VIIRS 375m Active Fire data. <https://firms.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/>

NCEI — NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information (2025). Marine data catalogue. <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/>

NOAA CoastalScience (2025). USA offshore wind lease ArcGIS service. <https://services2.coastalscience.noaa.gov/>

NOPTA — National Offshore Petroleum Titles Administrator (2025). Australia offshore petroleum titles register. <https://www.nopta.gov.au/>

NSTA — North Sea Transition Authority (2025). UK Continental Shelf oil/gas and carbon storage licences. <https://www.nstauthority.co.uk/>

NZP&M — New Zealand Petroleum and Minerals (2025). Online permit register. <https://www.nzpam.govt.nz/>

Ocean Networks Canada Society (2025). Oceans 3.0 Data Portal. University of Victoria. <https://data.oceannetworks.ca/>

OBIS (2025). Ocean Biodiversity Information System. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO. <https://obis.org/>

OBIS (25 March 2025). OBIS Occurrence Data — Open Data parquet snapshot. Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.25607/obis.occurrence.b89117cd>. Distributed at s3://obis-open-data/occurrence/ (~50 GB GeoParquet across ~6,900 files).

OpenAQ (2025). Air Quality Data Platform v3. <https://openaq.org/>

PANGAEA (2025). Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science. Alfred-Wegener-Institut + MARUM. <https://www.pangaea.de/>

PASA — Petroleum Agency of South Africa (2025). Offshore petroleum geoportal. <https://geoportal.petroleumagencyrsa.com/>

Pekel, J-F., Cottam, A., Gorelick, N., Belward, A.S. (2016). High-resolution mapping of global surface water and its long-term changes. *Nature* 540, 418-422. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20584>

PERUPETRO via INGEMMET (2025). Peru petroleum lots (zocalo / offshore). <https://www.perupetro.com.pe/>

PMP — Petroleum Management Programme of Guyana (2025). Auction blocks. <https://petroleum.gov.gy/>

SBMA / Landfolio (2025). Cook Islands seabed mining authority tenements. <https://sbma.landfolio.com/>

Scripps Institution of Oceanography (2025/2026). SIO-BIC — Scripps Benthic Invertebrate Collection. University of California San Diego. <https://sioapps.ucsd.edu/collections/bi/>. Bulk export endpoint: <https://sioapps.ucsd.edu/collections/bi/api/export/?taxa=all>

Sodir / NPD — Norwegian Offshore Directorate (2025). FactMaps petroleum and CO2 storage REST services. <https://factmaps.sodir.no/>

Taylor, J. (2024). ports.json — global port locations dataset. <https://github.com/tayljordan/ports>

Tucker, T., Giglio, D. et al. (2020). Argovis: A Web Application for Fast Delivery, Visualization, and Analysis of Argo Data. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology* 37(6), 1081-1097.

UNEP-WCMC and IUCN (2025). Protected Planet: The World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA), April 2025 release. Cambridge, UK. <https://www.protectedplanet.net/>

UNESCO (2025). World Heritage Marine Programme. Via Flanders Marine Institute MarineRegions WFS.

USGS (2025). Earthquake Hazards Program Real-time Feeds. <https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/feed/>

Yesson, C., Letessier, T.B., Nimmo-Smith, A. et al. (2020). Improved bathymetry leads to more than 4000 new seamount predictions in the global ocean. PANGAEA. <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.921688>